

Two Forces, Two Energies and Special Relativity for a Radiating Charge? Part 2

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In Part I, we tried to argue that a potential $V(r \text{ vector})$ may be associated with a rest mass, such that Force = $-\text{grad } V(r \text{ vector})$ according to Newtonian mechanics, but at the same time, if this mass accelerates, one might accept a $V(r) dv/dt$ type of force term (symbolic form). We noted, however, that this seems to arise in practice only for electromagnetism for which $V(r \text{ vector}) dv/dt$ does not drop-off as fast as $-\text{grad } V(r \text{ vector})$ and indicates that photons are being emitted by the charged rest mass. We then tried to link this scenario with special relativity arguing that $V(r) dv/dt$ not dropping off quickly may indicate that it is energy which has broken off from the rest mass particle. We suggest that $V(r \text{ vector}) dv/dt$ force is associated with energy and momentum which are not linked with a rest mass and so may account for the upper bound speed c which appears in special relativity.

On the other hand, in (1), we argued that special relativity is largely linked to impedance, with m_0 , rest mass, representing such an impedance. We further argued that adding energy to this rest mass may increase the impedance (e.g. m_0 is impedance/inertia, and momentum is linked with impulse, so why shouldn't the extra $KE = .5mv^2$ (nonrelativistic result) also be linked with impedance as it is $.5 p v$ (i.e. momentum flux)?

In this note, we consider this idea of impedance and note that m_0 is already associated with a gravitational potential in Newtonian mechanics, yet only m_0 appears in special relativistic expressions. This seems to suggest that one should not use the $V(r \text{ vector}) dv/dt$ argument for gravity. This begs the question: Why should the electromagnetic case be special, i.e. have accelerating photons? We suggest here that in the electromagnetic case, there seem to be two impedance parameters, m_0 rest mass, and q charge. In other words, q is an impedance only linked with the electrostatic and magnetic potentials and corresponding electric and magnetic fields. As a result, there is an impedance linked with m_0 , which includes electrostatic energy (and presumably bound electric and magnetic energy in the moving frame), i.e. one may consider the problem only in terms of m_0 , but at the same time one may link the pure electromagnetic features (electric and magnetic fields) with q (charge) impedance. Thus, there is a dichotomy in a moving charge. In such a case, it may make sense to consider $V(r \text{ vector}) dv/dt$ (symbolic form) because $V(r \text{ vector})$ linked with the electromagnetic field is actually associated with an impedance which should exist in the electric and magnetic fields. These are, it is true, linked to the source charge q , but physical impedance as well and energy and momentum should actually exist in space far away from a charge and so should have the possibility of "breaking off" and forming its own particle moving at speed c . This is a strange scenario, but the idea of an upper bound speed c in special relativity, presumably linked with a self-wave (no medium) and no rest mass is equally unusual and the two ideas may be compatible. Thus, we argue that the electromagnetic case is unusual in that it contains two impedances, m_0 and q .

The Notion of an Accelerating Potential

If one has a potential $V(\mathbf{r})$, then according to Newtonian mechanics, it is associated with a force: $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$, but is probably linked with a rest mass, m_0 as well. In other words, $V(\mathbf{r})$ does not simply exist in space without a source. If this source rest m_0 is accelerated, then one might try to argue that one has:

$V(\mathbf{r}) \frac{dv}{dt}$ acting like a force ((1))

if one is to take the notion of $V(\mathbf{r})$ as potential energy as being equivalent to rest mass energy (which may actually not be the case except in a very special situation.) One may see that ((1)) does not drop-off in space as quickly as $-\text{grad } V(\mathbf{r})$. In Part I, we argued that someone making measurements might mistake ((1)) for a force no longer associated with the source m_0 . This scenario appears physically, however, in the electromagnetic case as accelerating charged particles radiate photons, but it seems that one does not see this kind of radiation for other kinds of forces.

In Part I, we tried to link the radiation speed c with special relativity. In other words, we argued that special relativity for a particle with rest mass m_0 automatically brings in an upper bound speed c which seems to be linked with a self-wave if there is no medium. We tried to associate this self-wave with ((1)).

Special Relativity and the Notion of Impedance

In (1), we tried to argue that special relativity is strongly related to the notion of impedance. Special relativity usually deals with relatively moving frame, e.g. a rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t from a frame moving with constant $-v$ is seen to have a different E and p . The question we ask is: What is m_0 ? It must be measured and this measurement is linked with impedance. One either performs an inertia measurement or a gravitational one and both involve force/impedance and are said to yield the same m_0 value. Thus, m_0 is an impedance. One may note that m_0 may be associated with a complicated object. First of all, there should be a gravitational potential (according to the Newton view) yet one only uses m_0 , secondly, there could be an electrostatic field which also has energy. This energy is presumably also part of m_0 (even though it is a very small contribution). E and p in the moving frame are also involved with impedance we argued in (1) because p is linked with impulse (a flux of m_0 which is inertial impedance) and $E = m_0 c^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ (nonrelativistic limit) should be the sum of two impedances, first because m_0 is one and secondly because $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 = \frac{1}{2} p v$ (i.e. a momentum flux $\cdot \frac{1}{2}$). Thus, we suggest that impedance is a key idea in special relativity.

In this note, we argue that m_0 is not the only impedance (given by a parameter which is the same in all frames), but that charge q in the electromagnetic case is also an impedance. This leads to an interesting notion because a charged particle should lead to two impedances, m_0 and q at the same time. We ask: What are the consequences of this?

Two Impedances, m_0 and q for a Charged Particle

Special relativity applies to a particle with rest mass m_0 and one may consider the special case of a constant speed. In such a situation, some of this rest mass is:

$$\text{Integral volume } \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \text{ Electric field dot electric field } \quad ((2))$$

In the moving frame, there is extra energy density (impedance) of $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \text{ electric field dot electric} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \text{ magnetic field dot magnetic} \quad ((3))$

In this case, this extra energy/impedance is part of $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.

As a result, one may argue that for a constant speed one need only consider m_0 and not worry about q acting as an impedance.

We suggest, however, that the impedance of q may have physical relevance as in an accelerating charge, which has an electrostatic potential, and leads to emitted radiation. In particular, the electrostatic potential, linked to an electric field is already part of rest mass and hence impedance and so part of a momentum linked with $m_0 v$, but the Lorentz transformed $q \phi = qk/r$ transforms to:

$$Q k/r \gamma(v) \quad \text{and} \quad q \gamma(v) \phi' \quad v = q/c \quad A \quad (\text{i.e. a magnetic potential which is like a momentum}) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, instead of simply having one momentum linked with rest mass only (including that from fields), the fact that q is like an impedance suggests that terms (electrostatic potential) linked with q transform like an impedance and are linked with their own exclusive momentum A . In other words, one sees field energy as somehow being tied to the rest mass or $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ of a charged particle, but also fields (electric and magnetic) being tied directly to q and having their own sense of impedance.

This, we argue, suggests the possibility of one type of momentum breaking from another. In other words, it is specifically the m_0 and q separate impedances which allow for the notion of a momentum which is not based on rest mass. How can this be? A (magnetic potential) is already a momentum which is not based on rest mass. Furthermore, one has the momentum density:

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} \text{ electric field} \times \text{magnetic field} \quad ((5))$$

A problem is that to have $V(\mathbf{r}) \, d\mathbf{v}/dt$ (symbolic form) actually break off on its own, it must separate from the m_0 core as well as the source charge q . One might argue that without q and current density there is no electric and magnetic field. That may be the case, but these fields are far from the charge and current source and represent physical momentum and energy which is only held by the charge. It is not far-fetched to think they might break off as a self-wave given that special relativity seems to include a speed c (upper bound and the same in all frames) for

the analysis of m_0 , a rest mass. In other words, one cannot have one without the other. This speed c , if applied to a physical object, seems to pertain to a self-wave which creates its own speed based on some parameters of space. As a self-wave, however, it must be linked with action/reaction and so some force scheme is necessary and this should not be linked to a force scheme only associated with rest mass m_0 (e.g. gravity or even the very short range strong force). As a result, a force scheme which has some independence from m_0 because there is a separate impedance q is the electromagnetic one and it is possible, we argue, that the second impedance based on q may be linked to the emission of photons from an accelerating charge.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity is associated with impedance represented by m_0 . In particular, various potentials/forces may be associated with the rest mass of a particle including Newtonian gravity, electromagnetism (Integral $\int \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} dV$) and the strong nuclear force. One does not worry about details about these, but only uses m_0 in special relativistic equations. The question then becomes: Why does c , the speed of light which is specifically linked to a photon appear? We suggest that in addition to m_0 being impedance, a charged particle also has q as impedance. Thus, one may Lorentz transform the electrostatic potential to obtain a ϕ' and a magnetic vector potential A which is like a momentum independent of mv . In other words, the impedance of q gives rise to fields which may take on their own sense of momentum without any rest mass being present. We suggest that such an object is compatible with c from special relativity, which is an upper bound speed, possibly from a self-wave (action -reaction forces) which is the same as viewed from all frames.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Newtonian Mechanics as the Driver of Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)